

ABOUT THE TRADITIONAL ECONOMY OF THE KARAKALPAK PEOPLE

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Annotatsiya: Qoraqalpoqlar yashaydigan ovul va qishloqlarda deyarli har qaysisida o'zining duradgori, taqachisi, arvasozi, egarchisi, etikdo'zi, zargari bo'lgan. Qoraqalpoqlar orasida yog'ochdan turli buyumlar tayyorlaydigan yog'ochsoz ustalar, chig'ir, qayiq, o'tov ustalari ham ko'p bo'lgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Sirdaryoning o'rta va quyi oqimi, Daryolar va ko'llar, Quvondaryo, Jonidaryo, Markaziy Osiyo xalqlari.

Аннотация: Почти в каждом ауле и селе, где жили каракалпаки, был свой плотник, сапожник, каретник, шорник, сапожник, ювелир. Среди каракалпаков было много столяров, изготавливавших из дерева различные изделия, а также плотников, лодочников, отовских мастеров.

Ключевые слова: среднее и нижнее течение Сырдарьи, реки и озера, Кувандарья, Жонидарья, народы Средней Азии.

Abstract: Almost every aul and village where the Karakalpaks lived had its own carpenter, shoemaker, carriage maker, saddler, shoemaker, and jeweler. Among the Karakalpaks there were many carpenters who made various products from wood, as well as carpenters, boatmen, and Otov craftsmen.

Key words: middle and lower reaches of the Syrdarya, rivers and lakes, Kuvandarya, Zhonidarya, peoples of Central Asia.

In ancient times, the Karakalpaks were engaged in agriculture, cattle breeding and fishing in the lands located in the middle and lower reaches of the Syrdarya. There is a debate that they were cattle-breeding people from time immemorial, and later began to engage in agriculture. One of the characteristics of this people is that they have not changed from a nomadic life to a settled life like many other peoples, but have been living a settled life since ancient times. The Karakalpaks practiced irrigation farming from time immemorial. For this purpose, they took water from Syrdarya and its

tributaries Guvondarya and Jonidarya and released water to cultivated fields through irrigation networks.

In agriculture, grain growing is mainly developed. Wheat, barley and millet, rice, sorghum, flax, sesame, alfalfa, and polizi crops are planted on the lands around the rivers and lakes. The water needed to irrigate crops was a matter of life and death. Due to the lack of water, a lot of quarrels and disagreements would arise, leading to big bloody conflicts.[1]

One tribe or clan often lived in conflict with another neighboring tribe or clan. The harsh conditions of that time, the violence of the local rich and nobles, and the harsh rules established by them would have caused a lot of bloodshed. Each Karakalpak village was located around the traditional canals (japs) attached to them, each of which had a drinking water supply (tributary). How much water to give to whom; It was decided by the mirab how many people from which village would participate in digging a channel (arna) to bring water from the river, and how many people would be allocated to water to clean the aran in the spring. Water flowed until a certain mazgil (time), for example, from early morning to noon, usually enough to irrigate two fields of land. In times of water scarcity, two households were given one bucket of water.[2]

In many places it was necessary to irrigate the land with the help of hand hoses. Water was pumped from one ditch to another with these devices. At the same time, a device was used to release water with the help of a foot. This method is used to release water to crops of small area. Water was pumped to the large cultivated fields with the help of a chute. The land is fed with manure and an old wall. Before plowing, the land was irrigated several times to wash off the salt. Then it was plowed with a plow (gunda - agash) twice, first lengthwise and then crosswise. Then the plowed land is leveled by crushing the pieces with a mola or dandene.

The harvest was reaped with a scythe. Threshing and threshing of grain was done in a style characteristic of the peoples of Central Asia.[3]

Karakalpaks mainly raised cattle and sheep. In the summer, they were raised on pastures, and in the winter, they were raised by hand. Ushoq - cattle were herded by herdsmen, herdsmen were herded by herdsmen, and small animals were cared for by shepherds or shepherds. In winter, cattle were kept in corrals or sheds made of branches, twigs and reeds, and stables, stables, and stables were kept in cellars.[4]

In the northern districts of Karakalpakstan, where the Muytin and Koldauli clans live, the population is mainly engaged in fishing. A device called kaza was made from reeds for fishing. Left, fishing in boats.

Fur industry is also well developed in Karakalpaks. Because there were a lot of different wild birds, fowls and animals in the lands where blackbirds live, especially

on the banks of Amudarya. That is why, in addition to other activities, the Karakalpaks occasionally hunted. They hunted duck, goose, pheasant, rabbit, saiga, gazelle.[5]

Almost every village and village where the Karakalpaks lived had its own carpenter, shoemaker, carriage maker, saddler, shoemaker, and jeweler. Among the Karakalpaks, there were many woodworkers who made various items from wood, as well as carpenters, boatmen, and otov craftsmen. Karakalpaks were also engaged in weaving, carpet weaving, felt-making. Carpet products were also exported to the market. There was a great demand for tandoors and ceramic dishes made by potters.[6]

Karakalpaks received grain for their labor, and had oxen or equipment for plowing the land. Saddlers (ershi) made saddles, including horse-back. Eight parts of the saddle are assembled and glued in this mold.

Urshik and ball were used for spinning. He used a simple loom called a loom to weave wool, rice, and carpets. Kenegas and Mangit women were extremely good weavers.[7]

The cargo was carried by the Karakalpaks in boats and carts. An ox was usually added to the cart. Two types of chariots were made: tat chariot and telegen chariot. Depending on which animal is added, it is called a horse cart, an ox cart, and a donkey cart. Oxen and donkeys were mostly used as working animals, and in some cases horses were used.

In short, the daily lifestyle of Karakalpaks is unique, they were engaged in all types of farming in their daily work. There is still a debate that the Karakalpaks were cattle-breeding people from time immemorial, and later began to engage in agriculture. This ethnic group did not move from a nomadic life to a settled life like many other peoples, but has been living a settled life since ancient times. This way of living is one of the characteristics of this people. However, the cattle breeding branch of the farm played an important role in their life and flourished, as evidenced by the above-mentioned data.

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